

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It is a pleasure to introduce the third regular issue of the volume 2016. We are very proud to announce that the **2015** impact factor of the journal has risen as compared to 2014. The impact factor is now **0.546**, the 5-year impact factor is **0.684**. This notable success is only possible because of the generous support by the J.UCS consortium, the excellent reviews and the promotion of our journal by the editorial board, the dedicated work of the publishing and technical teams, and last but not least, because of the high quality contributions of the authors. Please allow me to express my sincere thanks to all of you who have contributed to the success of our journal.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce 7 accepted papers from authors of 6 different countries.

In a collaborative work between Russia and USA, Aleksei F. Deon and Yulian A. Menyayev focus in their article on the complete set simulation of stochastic sequences without repeated and skipped elements. A semantic approach for compliance validation of service-oriented architectures is introduced by Haroldo Maria Teixeira Filho, Leonardo Guerreiro Azevedo and Sean Wolfgang Matsui Siqueira from Brazil. In a collaborative research between Japan and Chile, Hiroaki Fukuda, Paul Leger, and Keita Namiki discuss an efficient and effective agent lookup for a mobile agent middleware. Josje Lodder, Bastiaan Heeren, and Johan Jeuring from The Netherlands cover in their work a domain reasoner for propositional logic. Guilherme Melo e Maranhão and Renato de Freitas Bulcão-Neto from Brazil discuss their research on a new approach for filtering semantic context towards supporting context dissemination. Gonzalo Rojas, Diego Seco, and Francisco Serrano from Chile introduce a novel point-of-interest recommendation approach based on a multi-granular characterization. Tiago Wiedmann, Jorge Luis Victória Barbosa, Sandro José Rigo, and Débora Nice Ferrari Barbosa from Brazil introduce their model for learning objects (LO) recommendation built on the similarity of sequences of LO in learning sessions. Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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